

Global Employee Relations: Business Strategies and Objectives

The Transnational Model of Multinational Organizations

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*See Global Employee Relations (ER): Home and Host Country Effects
(Spring 2012, Revised Fall 2016)*

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Abstract

Employee relations practices and policies, particularly in the global market, are subject to multiple political, legal, and institutional contexts. Moreover, market preferences are changing frequently causing organizations to adapt their development and manufacturing methods; thereby, requiring changes to business objectives and strategies. The theoretical framework for this paper will be changing business strategies and objectives in the transnational model of multinational organizations. The questions are: In the transnational model of multinational organizations, what is the relationship, if any, between business strategies and objectives and global employee relations practices and policies? What are the key issues?

Keywords: Global Employee Relations; Global Market; Transnational Model

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(Excerpts from Zeller, Spring 2012, Revised Fall 2016)

Business objectives and strategies, particularly in the global market, are subject to multiple political, legal, and institutional contexts; thereby, influencing the transfer of global employee relations practices and policies. For instance, the contexts can influence whether the home country's approach to global employee relations is seen as a model to be copied or as a departure from acceptable standards. The issue is further complicated in that global employee relations involves numerous organizational actors with varying levels of influence (Edwards, 2004, p. 392).

Within that venue, global employee relations are evolving as technology is contributing to the development of a borderless market; thereby, changing the specific ethnocentric focus to one that is pluralist and cosmopolitan. Hence, organizations will need to adapt global employee relations to keep up with changes in formal and informal systems. Nevertheless, in situations where United States multinational corporations are pressed to implement some of these changes in their offshore facilities, opposing foreign regulations and policies have thwarted plans (Zeller, 2017).

Organizational structure is another factor in transferring global employee relations. The transnational model of multinational organizations, selected for this research, invites the transfer of practices to, from, and within the affiliates; parent organizations and subsidiaries are aware of their own role as well as the role of others (Bartlett & Ghoshal, 1989). There is high pressure for integration and high pressure for differentiation; knowledge and innovation is developed and distributed within the entire organization. In the transnational model, the practice of knowledge sharing also recognizes the benefits gained from local responsiveness and adaptation (Bartlett &

Ghoshal, 2009). (Appendix A: Bartlett and Ghoshal's Four Models of Multinational Organizations).

Furthermore, transnationals "are among the world's biggest economic institutions"; thus, the study has socioeconomic, political, and legal relevance (Greer & Singh, 2000). The automotive industry, selected for this study, is relevant in that the "the top five players have a significant 49% share of the global automobile market" (Kallstrom, 2015). Although smaller automotive companies have taken this share away, in terms of vehicles produced, General Motors (GM), Ford (F), Volkswagen, and Toyota (TM), remain in the top five (Kallstrom, 2015).

The overall objective of this paper will be to identify any relationship between global employee relations and business strategies and objectives in the transnational model of multinational organizations. Whether global employee relations influence or is influenced by the business strategies and objectives in the transnational model of multinational organizations is one part of the issue. Another possibility to be considered is that the formal practices and policies may differ from the actual global employee relations practices.

Definitions of Terms

The following is a list of general terms, as applied to the topic of this paper.

Employment Relationship: Basically, 'businesses could not survive without their employees, who enable them to provide goods and services to their customers and clients. The relationship through which this is carried out is known as the 'employment relationship' (Aylott, 2014, p. 17).

Employee Relations: "Communications between management and employees concerning workplace decisions, grievances, conflicts, problem resolutions, unions, and issues of collective

bargaining” (BusinessDictionary.com, n.d.).

Industrial Relations: “Employer-employee relationships that are covered specifically under collective bargaining and industrial relation laws” (BusinessDictionary.com, n.d.).

Labor Relations: “The ongoing relationship between an employer and union members or other defined groups of employees” (YourDictionary.com, n.d.).

Business Objectives and Strategies: “A business objective is a result that a company aims to achieve. It also includes the strategies that people will use to get there” (Market Business News, n.d.). The business strategy “is a long term plan of action designed to achieve a particular goal or set of goals or objectives” (Rapid Business Intelligence Success, n.d.)

Transnational Organizations: Based on Bartlett and Ghoshal’s models of globalization (1989), the transnational approach, selected for this research, invites the transfer of practices to, from and within the affiliates; parent organization and subsidiaries are aware of their own role as well as the role of others. There is high pressure for integration and high pressure for differentiation; knowledge and innovation is developed and distributed within the entire organization. In the transnational model, the practice of knowledge sharing also recognizes the benefits gained from local responsiveness and adaptation (Bartlett & Ghoshal, 2009).

Objective (Excerpts from Zeller, Spring 2012, Revised Fall 2016)

Prior research titled “Global Employee Relations (ER): Home and Host Country Effects” (Zeller, Spring 2012, Revised Fall 2016) identified some of the employee relations (ER) challenges for expanding global corporations. In that paper, a conceptual analysis of global employee relations included the influences of communication, existing employee policies, corporate strategies, legislation, employee representation, and trade unions. Hofstede’s cultural

framework was applied to the predominant question: How do the value models and cultures impact the global employment relations practices and policies? (Almond, Edwards, & Clark, 2003, p. 432).

In this research, the overall objective will be to identify key issues in “Global Employee Relations (ER) In The Transnational Model of Multinational Organizations”. The theoretical framework for this paper will be business strategies and objectives in the transnational model of multinational organizations. The questions are: In the transnational model of multinational organizations, what is the relationship, if any, between business strategies and objectives and global employee relations practices and policies? What are the key issues?

Problem Statement (Excerpts from Zeller, Spring 2012, Revised Fall 2016).

Overall, firms experience a lack of alignment between employee relations and the corporate strategy and culture; a lack of commitment of line management to implement employee relations policies; and a lack of flexibility in the employee relations policies themselves to meet shifting business demands; thereby, indicating the relevance of understanding the impact of global employee relations (The Pennsylvania State University, 2012). In this paper, the objective will be to understand the relationships of global employee relations and shifting business strategies and objectives in the transnational model of multinational organizations.

Research Method and Design

The qualitative method will be applied to describe the characteristics of the population; the transnational model of multinational organizations (Adams & Lawrence, 2015). In addition, the qualitative design will allow “the study of things in their natural settings.”; thereby,

"attempting to make sense of or interpret, phenomena in terms of the meanings people bring to them" (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011, p. 3). Moreover, "only qualitative methods are sensitive enough to allow the detailed analysis" of changing organizational business strategy and objectives; and the relationship, if any, with global employee relations. (Cassell & Symon, 1994, p. 1).

"Widely used in organizational studies and across the social sciences", the exploratory, case study research strategy will provide the framework for an in-depth analysis of global employee relations in the transnational model of multinational organizations (Kohlbacher, 2006, p. 3). A within-case analysis will provide "a detailed description of each case and themes within the case" (Vohra, 2014, p. 59). Then, "a thematic (recurring) analysis across the cases" will be used to "search for themes that emerge as being important to the development of the phenomenon" (Vohra, 2014, p. 59). The aim will be to identify the impact of the relationships, if any, between the business strategies and objectives and global employee relations.

Accordingly, the approach for Joan Woodward's 'Management and Technology, Problems of Progress Industry' (1958) was based on "the belief that responsible officials on both sides of industry feel the need to digest and use new research material but have not the time to browse through full-length volumes" (Preface, 1958). Following Woodward's objective, this paper will "present briefly and simply -- problems arising from" changing business strategies and objectives, and global employee relations (Preface, 1958). Nevertheless, the time to browse and digest new information is dependent upon the reader. For some, the length of a presentation will be viewed as a limitation of the research design (Zeller, 20180).

Conceptual Framework (Excerpts from Zeller, Spring 2012, Revised Fall 2016)

Frameworks help us to break down business objectives into functional parts. Whereas prior research (Zeller, Spring 2012, Revised Fall 2016) relied on Hofstede's 5 fundamental dimensions of national cultures to enhance the understanding of global employee relations; this research will be based on business strategies and objectives in the transnational model of multinational organizations.

The following conceptual frameworks are presented as a basis for understanding some of the challenges that are faced in transferring global employee relations practices and policies – and the interrelationship with business strategies and objectives. In this section, the within-case analysis will provide “a detailed description of each case and themes within the case” (Vohra, 2014, p. 59).

Communications (Excerpts from Zeller, Spring 2012, Revised Fall 2016)

One aspect of global employee relations is the influence of business organizations on communication between management and employees concerning workplace decisions.

From a business perspective, in the well-known airbag recall, Takata wanted “to catch up and grab market share by being technologically sophisticated” (Berfield, Trudell, Fisk & Plungis, 2016). However, the case also “demonstrates one of the pitfalls of the automobile industry's global supply chain. Automakers increasingly buy identical parts from the same provider when that part is common to all vehicles, meaning product deficiencies may then affect a wider swath of the market than in the past” (Overly, 2017). “Even though the product range is wide, the market continues to be dominated by a few major companies” (Kallstrom, 2015). Some of the reasons for this is due to consumer brand recognition. Another is that, from an economic

standpoint, there are “significant entry and exit barriers” and “economies of scale” (Kallstrom, 2015).

Basically, airbags “aren’t filled with air, they’re filled with gas created by a burning propellant (Berfield, Trudell, Fisk & Plungis, 2016). Initial Takata airbags, filled with sodium azide, left a residue in the automobiles (Berfield, Trudell, Fisk & Plungis, 2016). Automobile manufacturers were looking for something that was cleaner. In spite of early warnings of limited supplies and costs, Takata was the first to use tetrazole. The chemical helped the company bring in Ford and General Motors, expanding its share of the North American market to 10 percent. Then, problems escalated when Takata added ammonium nitrate. Though other companies decided against using ammonium nitrate because of its instability brought on by temperature changes, Takata proceeded to include it in their new design. Ultimately, “because of their chemistry, Takata’s devices became less stable over time” (Berfield, Trudell, Fisk & Plungis, 2016).

Key Global Employee Relations Issues:

One aspect of global employee relations is the influence of business organizations on communication between management and employees concerning workplace decisions.

In this case, knowledge about the defects in the airbags was communicated; however, the workforce was not empowered to share information throughout the system. Concerns from Takata employees were discounted by the company executives. The executives also hid the “potential dangers” from their largest customer, Honda, and from United States regulators (Berfield, Trudell, Fisk & Plungis, 2016). In essence, executive decisions to block communications regarding the defects were driven by business strategies and objectives.

Honda's hierarchy defended its long-term business partner and maker of the defective airbags, Takata. As a result, it was almost 4 years before any announcements were made and the first cars were recalled (Mullen, 2017). The financial impact caused Japan's Takata to file for bankruptcy protection in Japan and in the United States (Mullen, 2017). Alternatively, their other product lines, steering wheels, seat belts, and additional safety products; continue to be successful. That success is attributed to "its skilled employee base, and geographic reach" (Mullen, 2017).

Employee Representation (Excerpts from Zeller, Spring 2012, Revised Fall 2016)

"Employee representation is systems in a company for considering employees' ideas and wishes, especially by having someone to represent employees at managers' meetings. Employee representation is going to be the driving force in industrial relations over the next five years." (Cambridge Dictionary, 2019).

At Volkswagen, engineers were confronted with problems in developing a diesel engine that met the requirements of the United States emissions testing. Under pressure to meet market and production demands, the decision was made to circumvent the requirements by developing a work-around where the engine would turn on emissions testing during the test; then turn off again during normal driving. Early in 2014, senior managers were informed about a study by the International Council on Clean Transport that showed "that Volkswagen diesels were producing far higher emissions on the road than in official lab tests." In response, a group of senior engineers formed a task force to "pursue a strategy of concealing the 'defeat device' in responding to questions from U.S. regulators, while appearing to cooperate" (Leggett, 2018).

Ultimately, in September 2015, Volkswagen announced that over 600,000 cars, “fitted with ‘defeat devices’ designed to circumvent emissions tests”, were sold in the United States (Leggett, 2018). Initially, the head of the organization’s United States Operations, Michael Horn, testified “to a congressional committee that the deception was the work of ‘a couple of software engineers’” (Leggett, 2018). Actually, the emissions testing was known by several upper-level managers, including the CEO, Dr. Winterkorn. However, “the scandal came to light because a single employee informed regulators what was going on” (Leggett, 2018). Though the investigation resulted in indictments, extraditing individuals to the United States is not allowed by some countries; thus, many have avoided prosecution.

Key Global Employee Relations Issues:

The employee relations issue is *employee representation; a system for considering employees ideas*, particularly through a representative at manager’s meetings. For instance, in January, 2016, when “the Environmental Protection Agency and the Department of Justice announced that they were suing Volkswagen...for violations of the Clean Air Act”, “managers made it clear to workers at the Volkswagen Chattanooga plant, that the company was actively monitoring social media and websites” (Elk, 2016). The stated reason was that “the company was negotiating a settlement with the federal government”; therefore, it was important not to talk to “the media or regulators about the ongoing emissions scandal” (Elk, 2016). Moreover, the workers were told “that they could be fired if they spoke publicly about the scandal” (Elk, 2016). Notably, “Volkswagen is challenging a United States National Labor Relations Board decision to allow maintenance workers at its Chattanooga plant to organize as a distinct group” (Boston, 2016).

Employee Relations Systems (Excerpts from Zeller, Spring 2012, Revised Fall 2016)

The *legal and voluntarist employee relations systems* may further affect the transfer of employee relations practices. The (legal) legislative system may require companies “to consult and negotiate with employee representatives”; thereby, providing a means of expression for the blocking or contesting of employment practices (Edwards, 2004, p. 390). For example, in the “German Works Council system, employees are entitled to rights of co-determination over key issues” (Scullion & Linehan, 2005, p. 166). Conversely, in the voluntarist systems, companies may consult and negotiate with employee representatives; however, the agreements are not legally enforceable. Thus, employees based in a voluntarist system might not be able to block or contest the transfer of practices (Edwards, 2004, p. 390). Ireland, the United Kingdom, and the United States are examples of voluntarist systems, in which “shop floor relations are often established according to managerial prerogative” (Scullion & Linehan, 2005, p. 166). In addition, in countries such as Hungary and the Czech Republic, the system is “dependent on attracting foreign investment”; therefore, it “tends to be based on industrial policy which appeals to international capital” (Scullion & Linehan, 2005, p. 167).

In this case, the manufacturing process for the Model 3, developed by United States-based electric vehicle manufacturer, Tesla, was described by CEO Musk as a production nightmare (Murphy, 2017). Likewise, workers complained that the long hours and the pressure to deliver vehicles were taking a toll (King, 2019).

Furthermore, at Tesla, security asked workers who were distributing union pamphlets to leave the premises (Murphy, 2017). The interference also included “managers attempting to prohibit workers from discussing union activities” (Murphy, 2017). Additionally, workers were

surveilled and ‘interrogated’; and, in some cases, fired. Tesla has “strongly denied the allegations, calling them ‘baseless’ and an attempt to discredit Tesla publicly in the media” (Murphy, 2017). However, during a National Labor Relations Board (NLRB) meeting, that required the attendance of Tesla CEO Elon Musk, the company was ordered to “explain employees’ rights to them.” Moreover, either Musk or his agent were to “tell employees that the National Labor Relations Board (NLRB) found Tesla to have broken the law” (King, 2019).

Key Global Employee Relations Issues:

The *United States* is a *voluntarist system*, in which shop floor relations are often established according to managerial prerogative. Hence, employees in a voluntarist system might not be able to block or contest practices (Edwards, 2004, p. 390). Conversely, the legislative system; as in Germany and France, may require companies “to consult and negotiate with employee representatives”; thereby, providing a means of expression for the blocking or contesting of employment practices (Edwards, 2004, p. 390).

During the critical production and release of its new Model 3, Tesla was “ruled as having interfered with union organizing” (King, 2019). Nevertheless, the NLRB “is limited in its ability to punish companies found to have violated labor law. While the agency can require that companies reinstate and pay back-wages to workers that were illegally fired, it can’t assess punitive damages or hold executives personally liable for violations” (Eidolson, 2019). Nonetheless, the decision does provide support for the United Auto Workers and California’s elected officials seeking “to tie electric-vehicle subsidies to companies’ workplace practices” (Eidolson, 2019)

Corporate Strategies (Excerpts from Zeller, Spring 2012, Revised Fall 2016)

There are three choices for *corporate strategies* towards employee relations: the *unitarist*, *partnership*, or *contingent approach* (The Pennsylvania State University, 2012). The *unitarist approach*, common to the United States, focuses on the goal to have the organization succeed in the marketplace. The creation of a common interest between managers and managed to achieve this goal is crucial to its success. However, the integration of this approach might be perceived as undermining the traditional practice in Europe to involve trade unions (Brewster, Sparrow, & Vernon, 2007, p. 189). On the other hand, the *partnership approach* accommodates work councils, such as those of Germany. The *contingent approach*, determined by the local context, accommodates the roles of the “state, legislation, unions and ownership patterns” (Brewster, Sparrow, & Vernon, 2007, p. 71).

The unitarist approach, common to the United States, focuses on creating a common interest between managers and those who are managed to achieve success in the marketplace. However, for General Motors, the market has changed; as a result, the common interests, along with the business strategies and objectives, have been revised.

For one, in the next several years, General Motors is recognizing that task-level automation will introduce changes that will result in some of the workforce being terminated (Lau, 2018). The “salaried and salaried contract staff is being reduced by 15 percent” (Lau, 2018). The reduction “includes 25 percent fewer executives to streamline decision making” (Lau, 2018). Then, over the next two years, the organization is doubling their resources for the electric and autonomous vehicle programs. Their strategy includes slimming down its product portfolio, “increasing modularization in their manufacturing process”, and lowering

development, production, and customization costs (Lau, 2018). Finally, General Motors is discontinuing the traditional models; e.g. Chevrolet Impala, Chevrolet Cruze, and Buick LaCrosse. In addition, their “flagship hybrid plug-in model, the Volt, originally designed to use its electric motor for short commutes, then switch over to the combustion engine for longer journeys”, is also being discontinued. The reason for discontinuing the Volt is that customer data indicates that the gasoline engines aren’t being used at all; “meaning that the car simply carries around a large, heavy extra engine with no benefits” (Lau, 2018).

Key Global Employee Relations Issues:

The *unitarist approach*, common to the United States, focuses on the goal to have the organization succeed in the marketplace. The creation of a common interest between managers and managed to achieve this goal is crucial to its success. However, at General Motors, customer data, indicating a preference for electric motors, led to a disruption that had been expected in the long run; not in the short run in which it occurred (Lau, 2018). Thus, the common interest fundamental to the goals for organizational success, when faced with the combination of workforce and market disruption, were revised. Moreover, at the workforce level, “skill sets developed 10-20 years ago are no longer valid in today’s digital economy”; thereby, leading to terminations and restructuring (Lau, 2018). The disruptions led to decisions to reassess the organization’s objectives and strategies; restructure the workforce; and modify product lines.

Discussion Points

For this paper, employee relations is defined as the communication between management and employees; relative to issues such as the influence of business organizations on communication, workplace decisions, grievances, conflicts, problem resolutions, unions, and issues of collective bargaining.

Organization	Case Study	Case Summary	Key Global Employee Relations Issues
Takata	Design for Air Bags	The influence of relationships with an outside supplier; e.g. Takata, on communication between the organization's management regarding the faulty airbag design.	Communication: Influence of Business Organizations on Communication, Workplace Decisions, & Problem Resolutions.
Volkswagen	Diesel Engines Emissions Testing	The issue of reporting faulty testing; e.g. to meet standards set by an external agency; suppression of union activities. Employee representation. a system for considering employees ideas, particularly through a representative at manager's meetings.	Employee Representation: Workplace Decisions, Conflicts, Problem Resolutions, & Unions.
Tesla	Production Schedule for Electric Cars / Autonomous Driving	The issue with production schedules and union activities. In the voluntarist systems, companies may consult and negotiate with employee representatives; however, the agreements are not legally enforceable.	Employee Relations System: Voluntarist: Workplace Decisions, Unions, & Issues of Collective Bargaining.
General Motors	Consumer Preference for Electric Cars / Autonomous Driving	The issue is General Motor's quest for the market of Electric Cars. Three choices for corporate strategies towards employee relations: the unitarist, partnership, or contingent approach. The unitarist approach focuses on creating a common interest between managers and those who are managed to achieve success in the marketplace.	Corporate Strategies: Unitarist Approach: Workplace Decisions, Problem Resolutions, & Collective Bargaining.

Thematic (Recurring) Themes

Due to changing customer preferences, there are disruptions in the market. Thus, organizational strategies and objectives are being revised; organizational structure is also being

adapted. The changes in production methods and product lines have caused job skills, that were once in demand, to become obsolete. In addition, task level automation is causing a workforce reduction, that includes management; e.g. layoffs and terminations. Other areas being affected by the competition to meet preferences and market demands are communication and negotiation. Generally, platforms to negotiate workforce issues and communicate ideas are either not available or are being obstructed.

Analysis

Consumer preferences has led to product innovation and production thereof, which in turn, has revised the organizational strategies and objectives; thereby, contributing to changes in organizational structure. Contingent Theorist, “Joan Woodward (1970) emphasized how changes in markets led to product innovation which then led to changes in technology and subsequently organizational structures” (Hinings & Greenwood, 2017, p. 135).

Woodward (1965, 1980), also recognized that with advances in technology and organizational structure, “the entire concept of authority in industry may have to change” (p. 30). As evident in the case studies, sharing knowledge that does not align with management’s ideas can cause conflicts that are fueled by emotions and subjective feelings (Hislop, 2013, p. 141). Furthermore, in light of the changes, the organizations fall into the “anchoring traps” that “tend to give too much weight to past events and not enough weight to other factors” (Hammond, Keeney, & Raiffa, 1998, para. 9). The avoidance of anchoring traps is particularly applicable in these situations in that they are characterized by the [global] marketplace; in which historical anchors can lead to poor forecasts and, in turn, misguided choices (Hammond et al, 1998, para. 9).

Given the workforce and market disruption depicted in the case studies, the challenge for Strategic Human Resource Management will be to create a linkage or integration between the overall strategic units of the business and the goals and objectives of its human resources (Çalışkan, 2010). Theorist, Kurt Lewin, in 2008, observed that “the main challenge in the twenty-first century is for Human Resource professionals to keep focused on a strategic role in their organization; e.g. contribution to strategy execution; while also performing the essential operational role”; e.g. measuring only Human Resource activities and workforce potential (competencies). (Bratton & Gold, 2017, p. 16).

Recommendations for Future Research

The objective for this paper was to identify the relationships, if any, between global employee relations and business strategies and objectives in the transnational model of multinational organizations. For the following reasons, the recommendation for future research is to identify the relationship, if any, between global employee relations and organizational structure. Contingent Theorist, “Joan Woodward (1970) emphasized how changes in markets led to product innovation which then led to changes in technology and subsequently organizational structures” (Hinings & Greenwood, 2017, p. 135). In each of the case studies depicted in this paper, market changes led to product innovation. The new products and production methods required changes in technology; thus, traditional job skills became obsolete, leading to workforce disruption; e.g. layoffs and terminations. The combination of market changes, product innovation, and workforce disruption contributed to changes in organizational structure. The question is: Is there a relationship, if any, between organizational structure and global employee relations?

Conclusion (Excerpts from Zeller, Spring 2012, Revised Fall 2016)

In this paper, employee relations is defined as the communication between management and employees; relative to concepts such as the influence of business organizations on communication, workplace decisions, grievances, conflicts, problem resolutions, unions, and issues of collective bargaining. Within that conceptual framework, the overall objective was to identify any relationship between global employee relations and business strategies and objectives in the transnational model of multinational organizations.

Based on the case studies, there is a relationship between global employee relations and business strategies and objectives. Fundamentally, changing market preferences contributed to revised business strategies and objectives. However, in the quest to meet the market demands, production issues were overruled, negative test results were modified, and union activities were suppressed. The changes also resulted in a disruption to the workforce; e.g. layoffs and terminations; including a reduction in management; that contributed to revisions in the organizational structure.

Primarily, communication between management and employees was not shared; or, when shared, the information was discounted, revised, or entirely suppressed. Generally, managerial prerogative was a major factor in the breakdown in the dissemination of knowledge. Conversely, in the transnational model, knowledge and innovation is developed and distributed within the entire organization; and the benefits gained from local responsiveness are recognized.

Overall, systems for considering employees' ideas, such as employee representation in meetings were suppressed. Union activities were discouraged. When ideas were presented, the issues were not provided with a platform for further investigation. Another factor was that in the

voluntarist systems, companies may consult and negotiate with employee representatives; however, the agreements are not legally enforceable. Hence, in that system, where companies did consult with employee representatives regarding issues such as production schedules, the negotiations were not legally enforceable.

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Appendix A: Bartlett and Ghoshal's Four Models of Multinational Organizations

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Transnational (Admin, 2009).

High pressure for integration - High pressure for differentiation

Strategy tries to maximize both responsiveness and integration, where knowledge and innovation is sought developed and dispersed within the entire network.

Distribution of resources is decided upon, as follows: Some are best-centralized within the home-country operation for several reasons: realize economy of scale, protect core competencies, and provide necessary management. Others may be concentrated but not necessarily at home, such as: world-scale production plants built in low-wage countries for labor-intensive products; advanced technology requiring a concentration of research and design resources and activities (Bartlett, Ghoshal & Beamish, 2008).

The structure of the MNC is regarded as a network, and each subsidiary is given responsibility compared to its capabilities and strategic mission.

The MNC is controlled by the movement of people within the MNC that may facilitate the mutual development and dispersion of innovation and knowledge.

Multidomestic / Multinational (Admin, 2009).

Low pressure for integration - high pressure for differentiation

Strategy is based on responsiveness to local market demands.

Resources are dispersed among the different national operations to be able to respond to local needs (Bartlett, Ghoshal, & Beamish, 2008).

Structure of the MNC will be a portfolio of rather autonomous national companies containing their entire value chain.

The innovation and knowledge developed at these national companies will most likely stay there, and will most likely not be dispersed to other companies within the MNC.

International (Admin, 2009).

Low pressure for integration - low pressure for differentiation

Strategy is based on home country expertise.

Resources are generally centralized in the home country for developing key innovations; however, other resources may be decentralized to allow innovations to be adapted worldwide (Bartlett, Ghoshal, & Beamish, 2008).

Structurally, the majority of the value chain will be maintained at the headquarters. The control of technologies used for e.g. production and general management systems will be structured and developed at home.

The development of knowledge and innovation will stream from the home organization to the subsidiaries.

Global (Admin, 2009).

High pressure for integration - low pressure for differentiation

Strategy is heavily based on scale of economies.

All of its resources are concentrated either in its home country or low-cost overseas location (Bartlett, Ghoshal, & Beamish, 2008).

From a structural standpoint, the subsidiaries of the MNC are rather weak and a full value chain will only exist at home. The subsidiaries are heavily dependent on resources and know-how from the home organization.

Innovation and development will be created at home, and later diffused to remaining subsidiaries.